

LEGAL AND BUSINESS FRAMEWORK OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN SLOVENIA AND THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract: *Social entrepreneurship is an innovative form of entrepreneurship that strengthens social solidarity, promotes volunteer work, and encourages collaboration among people. The goals of social entrepreneurship lie in creating new jobs for individuals who are vulnerable and have fewer employment opportunities. Through their activities, social enterprises contribute to solving social, economic, environmental, and other societal challenges. This work presents social enterprise as an innovative form of entrepreneurship. It also outlines the legal and business framework for the regulation of social entrepreneurship in Slovenia and the European Union, the institutions that promote social entrepreneurship in Slovenia, and social entrepreneurship as one of the core strategic development goals of the European Union.*

Keywords: *Social enterprise, social entrepreneurship, jobs, regular employment, legal and business framework of social entrepreneurship regulation.*

1. Introduction

The beginnings of social entrepreneurship or the social economy in Slovenia date back to the 19th century. Social entrepreneurship involves the creation of enterprises whose main goal is not solely profit, but the resolution of social and environmental challenges. Through their operations, social enterprises contribute to addressing social, economic, environmental, and other societal problems in an innovative way, while also providing employment and social inclusion for vulnerable groups. Generally, it can be defined that the primary goal of social entrepreneurship is not profit generation, but rather the promotion of cooperation, volunteer work and investment, and the search for innovative business solutions that pursue social, environmental, economic, and other goals in the context of strengthening social solidarity.

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Social entrepreneurship focuses on creating new jobs, particularly for vulnerable target groups in the labor market, such as persons with disabilities and older unemployed job seekers. The fundamental characteristic of a social enterprise is to provide regular employment for individuals who are less employable or otherwise disadvantaged. Two essential goals of social enterprises are, first, to provide a supportive environment in which individuals can develop their skills—one of the conditions for being a productive worker. Secondly, a social enterprise should enable or ensure permanent employment for its employees.

2. Characteristics of Social Entrepreneurship

Social enterprises are in many ways similar to traditional businesses, yet they differ significantly in their goals. The strategic objectives of social enterprises differ from those of conventional, profit-oriented companies. The specific legal form of a social enterprise is not the most important factor—what matters most is the participatory approach. Social enterprises reinvest their profits back into their activities. Their main goal is focused on achieving social objectives. Therefore, the relationships these enterprises maintain with customers, communities, public institutions, or other social enterprises are based more on cooperation than on market competition.

Social enterprises are structured around interest groups and typically include both regularly employed staff and volunteers.

“In comparison to traditional businesses, social enterprises face a higher level of economic risk related to ongoing production activities—namely, the production of goods and services for sale. A social enterprise is not a charitable organization, but a business in the full sense of the word. It must cover all of its own costs while simultaneously achieving its set socially beneficial goals. A social entrepreneur, who leads the enterprise, thinks and acts differently than someone heading a charity. The fact that a social enterprise is, first and foremost, a business, allows for its definition and the evaluation of its impact within the community” (Yunus, 2009, p. 39).

Characteristics of social entrepreneurship are as follows:

- Represents a new, alternative way of addressing social problems.
- An innovative approach that uses entrepreneurial skills to achieve social goals and solve societal issues.
- Seeks new market niches and business opportunities.
- Democratically managed enterprises, where decision-making is not based on the share of invested capital.
- High degree of autonomy (voluntary decision to establish the enterprise).
- Operates for the benefit of its members, users, the community, and vulnerable groups.
- Active involvement of all stakeholders.
- Prioritizes the growth of social capital over profit generation.

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- Market-oriented.
- Profits and revenue surpluses are reinvested into the activity or the local community.
- The primary goal of social enterprises is to serve the needs of members or the broader public.
- Provides services that are not typical for conventional entrepreneurs.
- Creates new jobs for vulnerable target groups with fewer employment opportunities.

3. Social Enterprise as an Innovative Form of Entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship is an innovative form of entrepreneurship, driven by the motivation to address social, economic, environmental, and other societal challenges. It is inherently collaborative, as it encourages people to work together and engage in volunteerism, thereby strengthening solidarity within society. Social entrepreneurship creates new jobs for vulnerable groups and carries out activities that benefit the public good. It represents an innovative business model that combines entrepreneurial methods with social objectives. Innovation in social entrepreneurship involves the search for and implementation of new approaches, models, or technologies aimed at solving social, environmental, or economic challenges - where the primary focus is on social impact rather than profit. Through their existence and operation, social enterprises respond to societal challenges, and by providing employment to people who face barriers to the labor market, they help reduce the risk of social issues arising.

"Social entrepreneurship is an innovative form of entrepreneurship that strengthens social solidarity, encourages cooperation among people, and promotes volunteer work. The goal of such entrepreneurship is to create new jobs for groups of people who are vulnerable or have fewer opportunities to gain employment. These include, in particular, persons with disabilities, first-time job seekers, former offenders, individuals with physical or mental impairments, people without formal education, those who are difficult to employ, and individual over the age of 55" (Pavel & Štefanič, 2005, p. 14).

Investments, in the context of innovative action, focus on combating unemployment, addressing social issues, mitigating the effects of economic crises, and solving environmental problems.

Social entrepreneurship can be defined as entrepreneurship with a social impact, aimed at ensuring a better future through innovative approaches to operation. By using innovative methods, it is possible to achieve outcomes that also contribute to social cohesion.

Figure 1: Dimensions of a Social Enterprise

Source: podjetniskiskladi.si/socialno-podjetnistvo/

4. Institutions for Promoting the Development of Social Entrepreneurship in Slovenia and Sources of Funding

"Social entrepreneurship certainly represents a potential for sustainable development, particularly from a local perspective, where it also offers an opportunity for the socio-economic revitalization of rural areas. The role of local-level actors is very important in creating a supportive ecosystem through collaboration. In this context, investing in the strengthening of social capital is essential" (Nerad et al., 2015, p. 105).

Institutions for promoting the development of social entrepreneurship in Slovenia are:

- Ministry of Economic Development and Technology. This ministry performs professional tasks in the field of the social economy and collaborates with relevant ministries in preparing legal frameworks, strategies, and measures in this area. It monitors the development of social entrepreneurship and maintains a register of social enterprises. It also issues public calls to support the operation and development of social entrepreneurship.
- Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities. The ministry promotes fundamental policies and mechanisms in the area of social development that aim to foster equal opportunities and enable social inclusion. This is achieved through investment in people and the evaluation of all social security systems, along with measures tailored to individual needs.
- Municipalities. Municipalities are responsible for planning, funding, and implementing social entrepreneurship development policies within their territories.

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One of the key characteristics of social entrepreneurship is its strong connection to the local environment and its responsiveness to specific local community issues, which often leads to the creation of jobs at the local level. This is particularly important in Slovenia in relation to the population of rural areas. Therefore, municipalities play a vital role in raising awareness of the importance and visibility of social entrepreneurship at the local level.

- Employment Service of the Republic of Slovenia. This institution supports the development of social entrepreneurship through various financial incentives for employers and by implementing public works programs. These programs have been part of Slovenia's active employment policy for many years.

Sources of funding can be divided into internal and external sources. Internal sources of funding primarily include own resources, with the addition of project-based financing provided by public funds through public calls. In terms of external sources, capital mainly appears in the form of institutional capital of a private nature.

Other methods of financing include non-repayable funds, subsidies, and donations that can be obtained from public sources. A significant source of non-repayable funding is also represented by European Union calls for proposals, through which funds are allocated based on programmatic instruments. Among the most important financial instruments for promoting the development of social entrepreneurship are the European Social Fund, the European Regional Development Fund, and various European Territorial Cooperation programs.

5. Social Entrepreneurship in the Legal System of the Republic of Slovenia

Until 2011, when the Social Entrepreneurship Act (ZsocP) came into force, Slovenia did not have a law that comprehensively regulated the status of public-benefit organizations. Despite this, social entrepreneurship already existed in Slovenia before the adoption of the ZsocP, in the form of entities/organizations that operated according to the principles of social entrepreneurship. To the largest extent, these activities were carried out by cooperatives, non-governmental organizations, particularly associations, and sheltered workshops for people with disabilities. Legally, these organizational forms were governed by individual laws: the Law on Associations, the Law on Institutions, the Law on Cooperatives, the Law on Employment Rehabilitation and Employment of People with Disabilities. The Law on Social Protection was the first law in Slovenia that legally regulated and defined the field of social entrepreneurship, the criteria for obtaining social enterprise status, maintaining that status, and the reporting and promotion of social entrepreneurship.

The Social Entrepreneurship Act came into effect in Slovenia on January 1, 2012. The law defines the concept, goals, and principles of social entrepreneurship, the activities of social enterprises, and the conditions under which social enterprises operate. It also outlines the conditions under which legal entities can acquire the status of a social enterprise, the process for obtaining and revoking this status, the special operating conditions for social enterprises, the records that are maintained in the field of social entrepreneurship, and supervision.

The law also regulates the planning of development and incentives for the development of social entrepreneurship, the cooperation of social partners and civil society

organizations in the adoption of development documents, the role of municipalities in planning and implementing social entrepreneurship development policies, and the responsibilities in the field of social entrepreneurship.

In 2018, the Act on Amendments and Supplements to the Social Entrepreneurship Act (ZsocP-A) came into effect. This law defines the concept, goals, and principles of social entrepreneurship, the activities of social entrepreneurship, and the conditions under which social enterprises operate. It also outlines the conditions under which legal entities can acquire the status of a social enterprise, the process for obtaining and revoking this status, the special operating conditions for social enterprises, the records maintained in the field of social entrepreneurship, and supervision.

The original law defined the activities that could be carried out within the framework of social entrepreneurship, which has now been removed, meaning that social entrepreneurship can be carried out in all areas of economic and non-economic activities. Similarly, companies were originally divided into two types, namely Type A and Type B, which has also been abolished.

The amendments to the Social Entrepreneurship Act have removed the requirement for a social enterprise to hire at least one person within one year of registration and at least two people within two years of registration. The key condition for employment in social entrepreneurship is a sufficiently large volume of income generated by the enterprise in the market. In addition to this, the amendment removed the restriction on registering the status of a social enterprise for sheltered workshops and employment centers. The change to the law also no longer differentiates between Type A and Type B social enterprises. Type A enterprises were those that carried out activities ensuring positive social outcomes, while Type B enterprises were those that employed a certain percentage of people who were harder to employ.

In addition to the umbrella Social Entrepreneurship Act, Slovenia also has subordinate regulations that more specifically govern the field of social entrepreneurship. The Social Entrepreneurship Act systemically defines the area of social entrepreneurship, and it is complemented by:

- The Regulation on Monitoring the Operations of Social Enterprises. This regulation governs the operations of social enterprises and the method for determining the fulfillment of conditions specified in the Social Entrepreneurship Act.
- SRS 40 – Accounting Solutions in Social Enterprises. It addresses the specifics of accounting in social enterprises, regardless of their legal organizational form, and is related to general accounting standards while also relying on international accounting standards.

These two subordinate regulations govern the way social enterprises operate and the fulfillment of the conditions for obtaining the status of a social enterprise. They prescribe in detail the content of applications, evidence, and reports required by the Social Entrepreneurship Act. They establish the conditions for eligibility for incentives and the methods for monitoring the eligibility of a social enterprise for such incentives. They dictate the manner of supervision over the use of financial resources received under the Social Entrepreneurship Act, as well as the process for returning improperly obtained financial resources and the conditions that an organization must meet to acquire the status of a social enterprise.

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6. Social entrepreneurship in the legal system of the European Union

Social enterprises, whose primary goal is to create positive social impacts, remain a significant part of the social economy in all European countries. They provide high-quality social services, create jobs for vulnerable social groups, and often respond to the challenges of sustainable development. Many are highly innovative in seeking development opportunities in areas where profit-driven businesses and the state have not been sufficiently successful in providing solutions. In this way, they make an important contribution to achieving the goals of various policies focused on job creation, social inclusion, sustainable development, and active citizenship.

The European Union has set social entrepreneurship as one of the core strategic goals for future development. A key document in this context is the Agenda 2020 for Social Innovation. Despite significant public interest, the field remains relatively underexplored, with relatively little known about the scope and characteristics of the sector across Europe as a whole. Social entrepreneurial practices vary greatly between countries because they stem from different national and economic frameworks, different approaches to the formation of state welfare, and cultural traditions.

Both in Slovenia and the European Union, there is a favorable climate for the development of social entrepreneurship. However, in many parts of Slovenia, there is still no adequate supportive environment for its broader expansion. The European Union plans to make certain financial programs more accessible for projects in the field of social entrepreneurship, which is linked to increased support for the social economy. This represents an opportunity for faster development of the supportive environment for social entrepreneurship in Slovenia as well.

At the level of the European Union, there is currently no unified, specific legislation for social entrepreneurship. The European Union 2020 strategy is the overarching strategy that advocates for jobs and smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth within the European Union.

Each country that is a member of the European Union has its own specific legislation on social entrepreneurship. However, there is a possibility that national legislation will contribute to the need for harmonization of social entrepreneurship legislation at the European Union level in the future. Laws on social entrepreneurship vary greatly among EU member states, which is why the European legal system seeks to limit legislation in the area of social entrepreneurship with at least a few provisions that national laws must comply with.

7. Conclusion

Social entrepreneurship in Slovenia has been gaining increasing importance in recent years. It presents a challenge in introducing new forms of employment for harder-to-employ individuals, while also playing a significant role in the development of economic activities.

In the European Union, or in member states, social entrepreneurship shares common characteristics, even though the regulation of the sector differs among European countries. The development of social entrepreneurship is more advanced in member states where social entrepreneurship has a longer tradition. It could also be said that, in EU member

states, the development of social entrepreneurship is aimed at addressing unemployment and creating new jobs in the competitive market.

The development opportunities for social entrepreneurship in Slovenia and the European Union are very good. It is primarily necessary to embrace this form of entrepreneurship. In the modern economy, where the focus is on competition and maximizing profits, and social issues are often sidelined, social entrepreneurship is definitely needed.

Social entrepreneurship must remain true to its core mission, target groups, and stakeholders.

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PRAVNO-POSLOVNI OKVIR SOCIJALNOG PREDUZETNIŠTVA U SLOVENIJI I EVROPSKOJ UNIJI

Rezime: *Socijalno preduzetništvo je inovativan oblik preduzetništva koji jača društvenu solidarnost, podstiče volonterski rad i saradnju među ljudima. Ciljevi socijalnog preduzetništva su stvaranje novih radnih mesta za ljude koji su ranjivi i imaju manje mogućnosti za zaposlenje. Socijalna preduzeća svojim delovanjem doprinose rešavanju socijalnih, ekonomskih, ekoloških i drugih društvenih problema. U radu je predstavljeno socijalno preduzeće kao inovativan oblik preduzetništva. Takođe je prikazan pravno-poslovni okvir uređenja socijalnog preduzetništva u Sloveniji i Evropskoj uniji, organi koji podstiču socijalno preduzetništvo u Sloveniji, kao i socijalno preduzetništvo kao jedan ključnih strateških ciljeva razvoja u Evropskoj uniji.*

Ključne reči: *Socijalno preduzeće, socijalno preduzetništvo, radna mesta, redovno zaposlenje, pravno-poslovni okvir uređenja socijalnog preduzetništva.*